

Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Self Administration of Insulin Injections

N. Sivasubramanian¹, Goswami Meghamaben², Prajapati Manoj³, Prajapati Mohit⁴, Prajapati Rinal⁵,
Prajapati Sumita⁶, Rabari Nilam⁷

¹ Professor, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University Visnagar, Gujrat-384315

² Nursing Tutor, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University Visnagar, Gujrat-384315

³⁻⁷ Final Year GNM Student, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus usually called diabetes sugar condition that occurs when the ones body does not produce insulin or body is enable to use normal amount insulin properly.

Objectives: The objectives of the study where on asses the knowledge and practice regarding the diabetes patient.

Design: a descriptive survey approach to assess the knowledge regarding self administration of insulin among the diabetes mellitus patient.

Tool: using 15 items questionnaire was in known portability conversing sampling technique the sample setting is selected area of kansarakui.

Sample Size: the sample size was 40.

Result: The study identify the 17 patient (42.55) having good, 16(40%) have average, and (17.5) poor knowledge administration of insulin among diabetes patient.

KEY WORDS: Administration, Diabetes mellitus, Knowledge, Insulin.

BACK GROUND OF THE STUDY

“No one gets to choose the challenges they face in life but they get to choose how they face it. “

“A wonderful affection not very frequent among men, being a melting down of the flesh and limbs into urine life is brief, disgusting and painful, thirst unquenchable, death is in evitable.”

Diabetes could be a serious, chronic disease that happens either when the pancreas doesn't produce enough insulin (a hormone that regulates blood glucose), or when the body cannot effect lively use the insulin it produces.

Lifestyle modification i.e. nutritional management exercise monitoring blood sugar level, education, etc. Plays an important role within the management of diabetes. With the advancement in life science and technology, pharmacological therapy i. e. Oral anti-diabetic agents and insulin therapy has a vital role in maintaining the blood sugar level among diabetes patients. Successful self management in diabetes helps the patient feel better. Education is a very important aspect of self-management, teaching the client on self administration of insulin helps the patient helps to create self-worth and pride of contribution in their management.

Insulin therapy has been proven to be effective in controlling blood sugar level among the diabetic patients. Insulin is employed to treat variety of diseases including Diabetes and its acute complications like diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperosmolar hyperglycemic States. It's also used together with glucose to treat high Blood potassium levels.

Aratus the Greek physician thus described the clinical features of diabetes, almost 4000 years ago. DM is an endocrine disorder. Characterized by hyperglycemias that's, high blood glucose levels. this can be caused thanks to a relative or absolute insulin deficiency, which may be a hormone produced by the pancreas.

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METHODOLOGY

The investigation was conducted in an descriptive survey approach setting. Kansarakui visnagar the placement of the study. The study was conducted in diabetes mellitus in kansarakui village. 40 diabetes patients on insulin therapy were selected for study. Using a non- probability convenience sampling technique. For this trial 40 DM patient were choosing. Purposive sampling could be a sample of knowledge who can give their response for the aim of meeting the target selected. Data collection tool are the instrument utilized by the investor to watch or measure the key variable within the research problem. The knowledge of diabetic mellitus patient regarding the self administration of insulin injections would be analyzed In term of frequency, percentage, mean, median, deviation, and would be presented table and diagrams.

Table 1:- sample frequency and percentage distributions based on demographic characteristics

Sr no	Variable	category	frequency	Percentage
1	Age	30 to 35 year	17	42.5%
		35 to 40 Year	3	7.5%
		40 to 50 Year	20	50%
2	Sex	Female	18	45%
		Male	22	55%
3	Education	8 Pass	3	7.5%
		10 Pass	22	55%
		12 Pass	15	37.5%
4	Occupation	Farmer	14	35%
		Job	26	65%
5	Family	Joint	20	50%
		Nuclear	20	50%

The data presented in table 1 shows the following findings: age: the majority of (42.5%) of sample were of the age group of 30-35 years whereas the least percentage (7.5%) were of the age group of 35-40 year. Sex:The highest percentages (55%) of sample were male and lowest percentages (45%) of sample were female. education; the highest percentage (37.5%) of respond had 12th pass whereas the lowest percentage (7.5%) is 8th pass. Occupation: majority of (65%) of sample were had job and (35%) had farmers. Family:in that family that both nuclear and joint family is equal percentage it is (50%).

Table 2:- Frequency and Percentage distribution of level knowledge and diabetes mellitus Patient

Level of knowledge according to diabetes mellitus	frequency	Percentage
Good (11 to 15)	17	42.5%
Average(10 to 06)	16	40%
Poor(6 to 0)	7	17.5%
Total	40	100%

Table 2 Shows frequency and percentage of knowledge about administration of insulin among diabetes mellitus patient and 42.5 % people have good knowledge 40% have average knowledge 17.5% patient have poor knowledge about it

Table 3: association of level of knowledge and self administration of insulin

Sr No	Variable	category	frequency	Level of Knowledge And perception			Table value	df value	Chi-square
				Good	Average	Poor			
1	Age	30 to 35	17	8	8	1	0.61	4	2.92
		35 to 40	3	1	1				
		40 to 50	20	8	7	5			
2	sex	Male	22	10	10	2	1.42	2	2.43
		female	18	7	6	5			
3	education	8 pass	3	1	1	1	0.41	4	2.18
		10pass	22	9	8	5			
		12pass	15	7	7	1			
4	occupation	Farmer	14	7	5	2	0.33	2	0.51
		job	26	10	11	5			
5	Family	Joint	20	10	6	4	0.98	2	1.67
		nuclear	20	7	10	3			

Table 3 shows that every variable level of knowledge is divided in good, average and poor. That the table value of every variable is right in that in age table value is 0.61, in sex is 1.42, in education is 0.41, in occupation is 0.33 and in family it is 0.98. in age and education the df value is 4 and another 3 variable sex, occupation and family in that df value is 2. the chi square of every variable is in age 2.92, in sex 2.43, in education 2.18, in occupation 0.50, in family 1.67.

DISCUSSION

Diabetes is a serious, chronic diabetes that occurs either when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin (a hormone that regulates blood glucose) or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin therapy has been proven to be effective in controlling blood glucose levels among the diabetes patients.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, data from the study provides data regarding knowledge about the self administration of insulin among the diabetes patients in the selected area of Kansarakui. In that age between 30 to 35 years and 40 to 50 years have good knowledge regarding self administration of insulin injection in Kansarakui village.

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